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Managerial Competencies and Employees' Trust in Management: A Study of the College of Business Administration in Jose Rizal Memorial State University

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ABSTRACT: This study assessed the managerial competencies and employees' trust in management at the College of Business Administration, Jose Rizal Memorial State University, during School Year 2025–2026. Specifically, it determined the respondents' profile, their perceived level of managerial competencies, their perceived level of trust in management, the significant differences in these variables when grouped according to profile, and the significant relationship between managerial competencies and trust in management. The study employed a descriptive-correlational research design using a structured questionnaire administered to 107 employees. Data were analyzed using weighted mean, standard deviation, and Spearman rank-order correlation. Findings revealed the perceived level of managerial competencies was very high, particularly in leadership skills and community collaboration, while human resource management obtained the lowest rating but remained very high. Likewise, trust in management was very high, with management integrity rated highest, followed by trust in management competencies and working relationship. A significant moderate positive relationship was found between managerial competencies and trust in management. The study concluded that competent, ethical, and development-oriented management strengthens employees' trust. It is recommended that the university enhance equitable human resource practices, strengthen campus-specific trust-building strategies, and sustain relational leadership practices.

KEYWORDS: managerial competencies, trust in management, leadership, higher education, employees, JRMSU

INTRODUCTION

Managerial competencies are essential in sustaining organizational success, especially in institutions where performance is closely associated with the quality of leadership. Competencies such as communication, decision-making, problem-solving, and strategic thinking help managers provide clear direction, strengthen coordination, and support employee motivation and productivity. When these competencies are effectively demonstrated, managers are better able to guide employees, respond to institutional demands, and promote organizational resilience in changing work environments (Alebiosu et al., 2022; Wziątek-Staško & Ryszewska, 2024).

This leadership requirement is particularly important in higher education institutions, where managers are expected to balance academic responsibilities, administrative functions, and human resource concerns. In this setting, effective management is not measured only by the ability to perform tasks, but also by the capacity to build confidence among employees. Managers who communicate clearly, make sound decisions, and address problems fairly are more likely to encourage employee cooperation, commitment, and alignment with institutional goals. Thus, managerial competence becomes a significant factor in creating a work environment where employees feel supported and motivated. However, competence alone is not sufficient; it must be accompanied by trust, since declining trust in leaders may weaken employee engagement, morale, and willingness to participate in institutional initiatives (Alebiosu et al., 2022; Wertz, 2022).

Managerial competencies and employees' trust in management are therefore closely connected. Leaders who consistently demonstrate fairness, sound judgment, transparency, and effective communication tend to develop stronger employee confidence. This confidence strengthens workplace relationships and promotes positive organizational behavior. In this regard, managerial competencies serve not only as indicators of leadership effectiveness but also as foundations for trust-based relationships between management and employees. Men et al. (2021) emphasized that effective supervisory communication is an important mechanism for building trust and enhancing employee engagement, showing that competent leadership contributes directly to the development of a trusting organizational climate.

Despite the growing literature on managerial competencies and organizational outcomes, limited attention has been given to how these competencies influence employees' trust in management within higher education institutions. Many existing studies on competency-based

leadership were conducted in corporate or business settings, making their findings less directly applicable to academic institutions with unique organizational structures, cultures, and accountability systems. Although previous studies in education have examined communication climate, leadership practices, and organizational trust, few have specifically investigated managerial competencies as a direct predictor of employees' trust in management. This gap provides the basis for the present study, which examines the relationship between managerial competencies and employees' trust in management within the College of Business Administration of Jose Rizal Memorial State University, where effective leadership is vital to academic delivery, administrative efficiency, and institutional performance.

LITERATURE

Managerial Competencies

Managerial competencies in education and public service and their impact on institutional effectiveness. In higher education settings, a systematic review identified transformational leadership, strategic management, digital fluency, human resource effectiveness, sustainability practices, conceptual thinking, interpersonal communication, technical expertise, time management, and effective decision-making as foundational for adaptability and institutional competitiveness (Connie et al., 2025). They further emphasize that emerging trends such as crisis management, data analytics, and cross-cultural leadership are increasingly necessary in a globalized education sector. Moreover, studies in the Philippines have documented the effect of managerial competencies of school heads and heads of public schools. For instance, Melgar and Ching (2022) showed that higher levels of managerial competencies and practices correlate with higher service quality in public elementary schools, indicating that competencies in leadership, management practices, and communication have tangible effects on the quality of education delivery.

Leadership Skills

Effective leadership skills — including vision setting, decision-making, communication, and the ability to shape school culture — are consistently linked to improved school performance and teacher motivation. Empirical studies show that principals who demonstrate transformational and instructional leadership foster positive school cultures that support teacher collaboration, higher Instructional Quality, and Better Student Outcomes (Tonich, 2021; Karataş, 2024).

Resource Management Allocation

Strategic resource allocation and transparent budgeting enable schools to match limited funds to priority programs and instructional needs; frameworks that guide layered funding, blended financing, and targeted resource deployment have been shown to improve implementation of school improvement efforts (Willis, 2019). Recent decision-making research also highlights data-driven criteria and participatory approaches as key to more equitable and efficient resource distribution in educational settings (Jafari, 2024).

Human Resource Management

Contemporary studies of human resource management (HRM) in schools emphasize that systematic HRM practices, including recruitment aligned to instructional goals, performance appraisal, and support mechanisms positively affect teacher engagement and performance; school heads' HRM approaches during crises (e.g., COVID responses) further underline the role of adaptive HRM in sustaining staff morale and continuity of instruction (Peña, 2023).

Professional Development

Ongoing, job-embedded professional development (PD), including coaching, collaborative continuous professional development (CPD), and training tailored to teacher needs, has been shown to improve instructional practices and student learning; meta-analyses and field studies find that sustained PD with follow-up (rather than one-off workshops) produces stronger teacher practice change and positive student effects (Aroca, 2022).

Community Collaboration

Partnerships and collaboration between schools and community organizations when reciprocal and well-structured strengthen support for students' academic and nonacademic needs, increase family and community engagement, and contribute to improved attendance and social-emotional outcomes; evidence reviews and implementation briefs recommend shared goals, clear roles, and sustained engagement as best practices for effective school-community collaboration (MDRC, 2021).

Trust In Management

Trust in management plays a crucial mediating role in influencing job satisfaction, organizational commitment, and employee well-being. Gopalan et al. (2023) found that trust in management significantly mediates the relationship between supervisor support, coworker support, meaningful work, and outcomes such as job satisfaction and healthy lifestyle, though it did *not* mediate turnover intentions in their large sample of working adults. This suggests that trust can buffer or reinforce positive work experiences even when other stressors remain. In another study in the Finnish context by Karhapää et al. (2022), trust arising from clear role definitions, transparent communication, and predictability during management change was associated with improved performance in both public and private sector organizations. These findings underline that trust isn't just a "nice-to-have" but rather a vital component during periods of change or ambiguity in management.

Trust in Management Competencies

Trust in management is often built on employees' perceptions of their leaders' competencies, such as decision-making, problem-solving, and strategic skills. Nguyen et al. (2016) emphasized that managerial competence strongly predicts trust, with employees more likely to view leaders as trustworthy when they demonstrate consistent expertise and effectiveness. More recently, Lazaro et al. (2022) confirmed that managerial competencies in communication, resource management, and leadership foster employee trust and enhance job satisfaction, indicating that perceived competence is a key foundation for positive organizational climates.

Trust In Management Integrity

Integrity is central to developing long-term trust, as employees rely on managers' honesty, fairness, and adherence to ethical standards. Abun (2022) found that managerial integrity directly affects employee trust, which subsequently influences organizational commitment and job

satisfaction. Similarly, Karhapää et al. (2022) noted that integrity expressed through transparent communication and fair decision-making during organizational change boosted employees' confidence in management and improved organizational performance, underscoring integrity as a trust driver in both stable and turbulent contexts.

Working relationship

The quality of working relationships between managers and employees has also been identified as a critical factor in fostering trust and collaboration. Lazaro et al. (2022) reported that strong leader-member exchanges enhance trust, motivation, and employee engagement, highlighting the relational side of trust-building. In a complementary study, Aziza and Nadia (2023) showed that employees with trusting relationships with management were less resistant to change and more engaged in their work, reinforcing that trusting working relationships are essential for both stability and adaptability in organizations.

Conceptual Framework

The conceptual framework is presented in Figure 1. First, managerial competencies with indicators categorized into leadership skills, resource management allocation, human resource management, professional development, and community collaboration. Second, the dependent variable is trust in management, with indicators categorized into trust in management competencies, trust in management integrity, and working relationships.

Figure 3. Conceptual Framework of the Study

Statement of the Problem

This study aimed to assess the managerial competencies and examine their effects on employees' trust in management at the College of Business Administration, Jose Rizal Memorial State University, during the school year 2025–2026.

Specifically, it sought to answer the following questions:

1. What is the respondents' perceived level of managerial competencies in terms of:
 - 1.1 leadership skills;
 - 1.2 resource management allocation;
 - 1.3 human resource management;
 - 1.4 professional development; and
 - 1.5 community collaboration?
2. What is the respondents' perceived level of trust in management in terms of:
 - 3.1 trust in management competencies;
 - 3.2 trust in management integrity; and
 - 3.3 working relationship?
3. Is there a significant relationship between the perceived level of managerial competencies and the perceived level of trust in management?

Hypothesis

1. There is no significant relationship between the perceived level of managerial competencies and the perceived level of trust in management.

Scope and Limitation of the Study

This study was limited to assessing managerial competencies and their influence on employees' trust in management within the College of Business Administration of Jose Rizal Memorial State University during School Year 2025–2026. Specifically, managerial competencies were examined in terms of leadership skills, resource management allocation, human resource management, professional development practices, and community collaboration. Employees' trust in management was examined in terms of trust in management competencies, trust in management integrity, and working relationships.

The respondents of the study were the one hundred twenty-four (124) employees of the College of Business Administration across the included campuses of Jose Rizal Memorial State University. However, personnel from the Siocon Campus were excluded because the campus offers only one program and was not comparable with the other campuses covered in the study. Therefore, the findings of this study were limited to the perceptions of the respondents during the period of data gathering and may not be generalized to other colleges, campuses, universities, or institutions.

Furthermore, the study relied on self-reported responses gathered through a structured questionnaire. Thus, the results were dependent on the honesty, understanding, and experiences of the respondents regarding managerial competencies and trust in management. Other factors that

may influence employees' trust in management, such as institutional culture, compensation, promotion systems, and personal work experiences, were not extensively examined in this study.

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

Method Used

The study included survey and descriptive-correlational research methods. The survey method was employed since the researcher gathered data through a questionnaire checklist of managerial competencies and employees' trust in management. Creswell and Guetterman (2019) defined a survey as a research method used for collecting data from a predefined group of respondents to gain information and insights on various topics of interest. On the other hand, correlational research is a type of non-experimental research method in which a researcher measures variables, understands, and assesses the statistical relationship between them with no influence from any extraneous variable (Bhat, 2019). A correlational analysis was performed to determine the significant relationship between managerial competencies and employees' trust in management.

Research Instrument

The research instrument was a structured questionnaire composed of three parts. Part I utilized the Managerial Competencies Scale (MCS) adopted from Abun et al. (2022), which consisted of thirty (30) items categorized into five dimensions: leadership skills, resource management allocation, human resource management, professional development, and community collaboration. Part II employed the Trust in Management Scale (TMS) also adopted from Abun et al. (2022), comprising ten (10) items grouped into three dimensions: trust in management competencies, trust in management integrity, and working relationships.

Ethical Consideration

This study secured approval from the Research and Ethics Committee of Jose Rizal Memorial State University before the conduct of data gathering. Informed consent was obtained from the institution and from the individual respondents. The questionnaire was written in clear and understandable language to ensure voluntary and informed participation. The respondents' identities were kept anonymous, and all information gathered was treated with strict confidentiality. Only essential research data were retained for academic and future research purposes.

Statistical Treatment of the Data

Presented below are the statistical tools utilized in the treatment and analysis of the data gathered.

Weighted Mean. This is used to quantify the respondents' ratings on the Managerial Competencies and Trust in Management. Presented below are the scoring guides for giving qualitative descriptions and interpretation of the responses to the items in Managerial Competencies and Trust in Management.

Scoring Procedure

Managerial Competencies

Scale	Range of Values	Description	Interpretation
5	4.21-5.00	Strongly agree	Very High
4	3.41-4.20	Agree	High
3	2.61-3.40	Somewhat Agree	Average
2	1.81-2.60	Disagree	Low
1	1.00-1.80	Strongly Disagree	Very Low

Trust in Management

Scale	Range of Values	Description	Interpretation
5	4.21-5.00	Strongly agree	Very High
4	3.41-4.20	Agree	High
3	2.61-3.40	Somewhat Agree	Average
2	1.81-2.60	Disagree	Low
1	1.00-1.80	Strongly Disagree	Very Low

Standard Deviation. This is used to determine the homogeneity and heterogeneity of the employees' scores, where $SD \leq 3$ is homogenous and $SD > 3$ is heterogeneous (Aiken & Susane, 2001; Refugio et al. 2019).

Spearman Rank-Order Correlation Coefficient (Spearman rho). This is used to determine the correlation between Managerial Competencies and Trust in Management. The following guide in interpreting the correlation value suggested by Cohen et al. (2014) was utilized in this study:

DATA PRESENTATION AND ANALYSIS

The data are presented following the statement of the problems of the current study. The study aimed to answer the following questions:

1. What is the respondents' perceived level of managerial competencies in terms of:
 - 1.1 leadership skills;
 - 1.2 resource management allocation;
 - 1.3 human resource management;
 - 1.4 professional development; and

1.5 community collaboration?

Table 1: Perceived Level of Managerial Competencies in Terms of Leadership Skills

A. Leadership Skills.	AWV	SD	Description	Interpretation
1. Engages in and promotes ethical conduct.	4.64	0.59	Strongly Agree	Very High
2. Uses and practices a participatory management style open to constructive criticism.	4.54	0.60	Strongly Agree	Very High
3. Seeks input from all levels of staff, listens attentively, demonstrates fairness and consistency, and conveys information fully.	4.50	0.65	Strongly Agree	Very High
4. Uses a variety of modes of communication.	4.54	0.69	Strongly Agree	Very High
5. Encourages and allows the opportunity for staff to confer and present issues and problems affecting instruction and other program-related services.	4.48	0.68	Strongly Agree	Very High
6. Supports innovative practices to improve program-related issues and services	4.41	0.71	Strongly Agree	Very High
7. Provides opportunities for learners, management, and community stakeholders to give feedback before significant program changes are implemented.	4.55	0.62	Strongly Agree	Very High
8. Delegates authority and decision-making to appropriate entities and supports their decisions.	4.47	0.63	Strongly Agree	Very High
9. Uses collaborative teams and other strategies to identify outcomes, design curriculum, share instructional strategies, conduct assessments, analyze results, and adjust instructional processes.	4.45	0.66	Strongly Agree	Very High
10. Present innovations to appropriate staff and make decisions that are aligned with their feedback.	4.42	0.71	Strongly Agree	Very High
11. Disseminates information in the community about program accomplishments through the use of technology and other means.	4.38	0.72	Strongly Agree	Very High
Overall	4.49	0.56	Strongly Agree	Very High

AWV=Average Weighted Value, SD=Standard Deviation

Table 1 presents the perceived level of managerial competencies in terms of leadership skills. The results show that the respondents perceived leadership skills as **very high**, as indicated by the overall mean of 4.49 and standard deviation of 0.56. Among the indicators, the highest rating was given to management’s engagement in and promotion of ethical conduct, with an average weighted value of 4.64. This was followed by providing opportunities for learners, management, and community stakeholders to give feedback before significant program changes are implemented, with an average weighted value of 4.55. Likewise, the use of participatory management and various modes of communication both obtained high ratings, with an average weighted value of 4.54.

This means that employees generally perceive their managers as ethical, participative, communicative, and open to feedback. The very high rating suggests that management demonstrates leadership behaviors that promote fairness, transparency, collaboration, and shared decision-making. These leadership practices are important because they help employees feel involved, respected, and guided in the attainment of institutional goals. This suggests that leadership skills are a strong area of managerial competency within the college. When managers demonstrate ethical conduct, encourage participation, communicate clearly, and involve stakeholders in decision-making, employees are more likely to develop confidence in management. However, management should continue strengthening inclusive leadership practices, especially for employees with different employment statuses and work experiences, so that all personnel will feel equally heard, supported, and represented in institutional processes.

The result is supported by Zhu and Zhang (2023), who explained that ethical leadership strengthens employees’ trust because workers are more likely to rely on leaders who demonstrate fairness, honesty, and consistency in their actions. Their study emphasizes that ethical leadership creates a work climate where employees feel secure and respected. Similarly, Nguyen and Tran (2024) stated that participatory and communicative leadership enhances trust because employees become more confident in management when they are given opportunities to share ideas, receive information, and take part in decision-making. Therefore, the very high rating in leadership skills confirms that management is perceived as ethical and collaborative, providing a strong foundation for employees’ trust in management.

Table 2: Perceived Level of Managerial Competencies in Terms of Resource Management Allocation

B. Resource Management Allocation	AWV	SD	Description	Interpretation
1. Ensures that expenditures are allowable and appropriate and that allocated funds are available throughout the fiscal year.	4.49	0.73	Strongly Agree	Very High
2. Evidence: - Allocates funds equitably to effective programs and sites based on such indicators as attendance, retention, student outcomes, and benchmarks.	4.45	0.68	Strongly Agree	Very High
3. Uses resources to integrate and upgrade technology and provides professional development on the effective use of technology for management and administrators.	4.36	0.73	Strongly Agree	Very High
Overall	4.43	0.66	Strongly Agree	Very High

AWV=Average Weighted Value, SD=Standard Deviation

Table 2 presents the perceived level of managerial competencies in terms of resource management allocation. The results show that the respondents perceived this competency as very high, as indicated by the overall mean of 4.43 and standard deviation of 0.66. Among the indicators, the highest rating was given to management’s ability to ensure that expenditures are allowable, appropriate, and supported by available funds throughout the fiscal year, with an average weighted value of 4.49. This was followed by the equitable allocation of funds to effective programs and sites based on attendance, retention, student outcomes, and benchmarks, with an average weighted value of 4.45. Meanwhile, the use of resources to upgrade technology and provide professional development on the effective use of technology obtained the lowest mean of 4.36, although it was still interpreted as very high. This means that employees generally perceive management as responsible, fair, and systematic in allocating and utilizing institutional resources. The very high rating suggests that management is viewed as capable of ensuring proper expenditures, equitable fund distribution, and appropriate use of resources to support programs and services. However, the slightly lower rating on technology upgrading and related professional development suggests that this area may still be strengthened to better support employees’ work performance and institutional operations. This indicates that resource management allocation is a strong area of managerial competency within the college. When employees perceive those resources are distributed fairly and used appropriately, they are more likely to develop confidence in management decisions. Nevertheless, management should continue practicing transparency, fairness, and accountability in budget and resource allocation, especially because employees may have different needs depending on their income level, employment status, and work assignment. Strengthening technology-related investments and training may also help improve employees’ perception of support and fairness.

The result is supported by Lee and Lee (2023), who explained that employees’ trust in management is strengthened when they perceive fairness in the distribution of organizational resources and transparency in decision-making processes. Their view suggests that fair resource allocation reflects both managerial competence and procedural justice. Similarly, Gupta and Sharma (2024) emphasized that responsible financial stewardship and equitable access to resources help employees view management as reliable and trustworthy. Therefore, the very high rating in resource management allocation confirms that management is generally perceived as fair and fiscally responsible, while the relatively lower rating on technology-related resource use highlights the need for continued investment in technology upgrading and professional development.

Table 3: Perceived Level of Managerial Competencies in Terms of Human Resource Management

C. Human Resource Management	AWV	SD	Description	Interpretation
1. Provides formal orientation of new staff and learners to the adult education program.	4.28	0.91	Strongly Agree	Very High
2. Provides for a system of management observations and evaluations focusing on such areas as (1) organizing and delivering instruction, (2) managing instructional resources,(3) monitoring and assessing progress, (4) accommodating diverse learning styles, (5) using materials and technology, (6) providing learner guidance and referrals, and (7) helping learners transfer learning to real-life situations.	4.29	0.81	Strongly Agree	Very High
3. Recognizes when staff members are not performing effectively, provides guidance and support to enable attainment of needed competencies, involves appropriate stakeholders, and follows required procedures and due process, leading to staff termination when necessary	4.22	0.83	Strongly Agree	Very High
4. Fulfills legal or program requirements for compliance, record keeping, and reporting.	4.37	0.80	Strongly Agree	Very High

5. Maintains confidentiality and limits access to staff and learner files and records (e.g. past education, employment, interests, disabilities).	4.46	0.76	Strongly Agree	Very High
6. Ensures data are accessible, promptly, to staff, learners, community members, and other stakeholders (via such means as reports, use of media, and web pages).	4.38	0.80	Strongly Agree	Very High
Overall	4.33	0.75	Strongly Agree	Very High

AWV=Average Weighted Value, SD=Standard Deviation

Table 3 presents the perceived level of managerial competencies in terms of human resource management. The results show that the respondents perceived this competency as **very high**, as indicated by the overall mean of 4.33 and standard deviation of 0.75. Among the indicators, the highest rating was given to management’s ability to maintain confidentiality and limit access to staff and learner files, with an average weighted value of 4.46. This was followed by the fulfillment of legal or program requirements for compliance, record keeping, and reporting, with an average weighted value of 4.37. Meanwhile, the lowest rating was given to management’s ability to recognize staff members who are not performing effectively and provide guidance, support, and due process, with an average weighted value of 4.22, although it was still interpreted as very high. This means that employees generally perceive management as capable of performing important human resource functions, particularly in protecting confidential records, complying with institutional requirements, and ensuring proper documentation. The very high rating suggests that management is trusted in handling sensitive information and following formal procedures. However, the relatively lower rating on staff performance guidance and support indicates that some employees may still expect stronger mentoring, coaching, and developmental assistance from management, especially when performance-related concerns arise. This suggests that human resource management is a strong area of managerial competency, but it also remains an area where further improvement may be made. Management may continue strengthening systems for staff orientation, performance monitoring, coaching, employee support, and fair implementation of due process. These practices are especially important in a workforce composed of both permanent and non-permanent employees, since inclusive and equitable human resource practices can help strengthen employees’ sense of belonging, security, and trust in management.

The result is supported by Chen et al. (2023), who explained that confidentiality, compliance, and fair administrative procedures are important elements of procedural justice because employees are more likely to trust management when policies are applied properly and sensitive information is handled responsibly. In the same way, Aboramadan (2022) emphasized that effective human resource management practices contribute to employee trust, particularly when organizations provide orientation, support, inclusion, and developmental opportunities for all employees regardless of employment status. Therefore, the very high rating in human resource management confirms that management is generally perceived as competent in performing formal HR functions, while the lower rating in performance guidance highlights the need to strengthen developmental and supportive HR practices across all employee groups.

Table 4: Perceived Level of Managerial Competencies in Terms of Professional Development Practices

D. Professional Development Practices	AWV	SD	Description	Interpretation
1. Keeps up-to-date with research on instructional practices, management, and leadership, as well as on effective practices in professional development, and shares those practices with staff.	4.46	0.68	Strongly Agree	Very High
2. Engages in a variety of activities that foster own learning such as participating in collegial networking and subscribing to journals.	4.37	0.73	Strongly Agree	Very High
3. Supports the professional development of management by stipends, or other types of support enabling management to relay specific information about professional development opportunities by providing release time, and engaging in professional development activities that focus on student and program improvement.	4.36	0.81	Strongly Agree	Very High
4. Encourages management to become involved in the identification and planning of their professional development and to engage in a variety of activities including inquiry research, workshops, institutes, and observation/feedback (e.g., peer coaching and mentoring).	4.48	0.69	Strongly Agree	Very High
5. Designs collaboratively, a staff development program based on the results of staff needs assessments, informal conversations, identified state or local needs and mandates, and research.	4.35	0.84	Strongly Agree	Very High

6. Supports a variety of professional development activities that reflect the organization’s mission and principles of adult learning.	4.36	0.74	Strongly Agree	Very High
7. Acquires and maintains knowledge of technology and applies it to adult learning and professional development.	4.36	0.72	Strongly Agree	Very High
8. Shares information on providing training in and promoting the use of technology with management and other staff	4.30	0.78	Strongly Agree	Very High
Overall	4.38	0.64	Strongly Agree	Very High

AWV=Average Weighted Value, SD=Standard Deviation

Table 4 presents the perceived level of managerial competencies in terms of professional development practices. The results show that the respondents perceived this competency as **very high**, as indicated by the overall mean of 4.38 and standard deviation of 0.64. Among the indicators, the highest rating was given to management’s encouragement of staff involvement in identifying and planning their own professional development, with an average weighted value of 4.48. This was followed by management’s effort to keep updated with research on instructional practices, management, leadership, and professional development, and to share these practices with staff, with an average weighted value of 4.46. Meanwhile, the lowest rating was given to sharing information on training and promoting the use of technology, with an average weighted value of 4.30, although it was still interpreted as very high. This means that employees generally perceive management as supportive of professional growth and continuous learning. The high ratings suggest that managers encourage staff participation in development planning, promote research-based practices, and provide opportunities for professional improvement. These practices show that management recognizes the importance of enhancing employees’ knowledge, skills, and competencies in order to improve both individual and institutional performance. This indicates that professional development practices are a strong area of managerial competency within the college. When employees are given opportunities to participate in training, planning, mentoring, and other learning activities, they are more likely to feel valued and supported by management. However, the relatively lower rating on technology-related training suggests the need to strengthen the dissemination of information and access to technology-based professional development. Management may also ensure that professional development opportunities, support mechanisms, and training benefits are implemented fairly and transparently across all employment groups, including regular permanent employees and visiting lecturers.

The result is supported by Kurtessis et al. (2024), who explained that employees’ trust and commitment are strengthened when management demonstrates organizational support through professional development, recognition, and opportunities for growth. Their view suggests that employees are more likely to trust leaders who invest in their learning and long-term improvement. Similarly, Sarti and Torre (2023) emphasized that collaborative and accessible professional development contributes to employee engagement because it allows workers to take part in shaping their own growth. Lee and Kim (2023) also noted that in academic institutions, professional development is especially important because employees value continuous learning, research engagement, and intellectual advancement. Therefore, the very high rating in professional development practices confirms that management is perceived as supportive of employee growth, while the comparatively lower score on technology-related training highlights the need to strengthen equitable and responsive development opportunities for all staff categories.

Table 5: Perceived Level of Managerial Competencies in Terms of Community Collaboration

E. Community Collaboration	AWV	SD	Description	Interpretation
1. Maintains ongoing agency outreach, publicity, and staff funding, community expertise, equipment, and other resources.	4.45	0.68	Strongly Agree	Very High
2. Establishes partnerships and alliances with businesses, institutions of higher learning, local educational agencies, child care centers, health centers, employment and job training centers, boards, and other agencies to expand understanding of adult education, assess needs, enhance program resources, and improve services for the adult learner.	4.50	0.64	Strongly Agree	Very High
Overall	4.47	0.63	Strongly Agree	Very High

AWV=Average Weighted Value, SD=Standard Deviation

Table 5 presents the perceived level of managerial competencies in terms of **community collaboration**. The results show that the respondents perceived this competency as **very high**, as reflected in the overall mean of 4.47 and standard deviation of 0.63. Among the indicators, establishing partnerships and alliances with businesses, institutions of higher learning, local agencies, and other community organizations obtained the highest average weighted value of 4.50. This was followed by maintaining ongoing agency outreach, publicity, staff funding, community expertise, equipment, and other resources, with an average weighted value of 4.45. This means that employees strongly perceive management as capable of building and sustaining external linkages that support the programs and services of the college. The very high rating suggests that managers are effective in connecting the institution with community partners, agencies, industries, and other stakeholders. These partnerships may

help expand institutional resources, strengthen program implementation, and enhance opportunities for employees, learners, and the wider academic community. This indicates that community collaboration is one of the strong areas of managerial competency within the college. When management is able to establish partnerships and maintain external linkages, employees may view their leaders as proactive, resourceful, and development-oriented. However, management should also ensure that the benefits gained from these partnerships, such as training, equipment, networking opportunities, and professional support, are distributed fairly among employees. This is especially important for both permanent and non-permanent personnel so that external collaboration will also strengthen internal trust and organizational support.

The result is supported by Cropanzano et al. (2023), who explained that employees tend to develop stronger trust in management when leaders demonstrate the ability to secure resources, build external relationships, and strengthen organizational legitimacy. Their view suggests that community collaboration reflects not only external engagement but also managerial competence in expanding institutional opportunities. Similarly, Akgunduz et al. (2022) emphasized that, based on social exchange theory, employees are more likely to trust management when they perceive that leaders act in ways that benefit the organization and support employee welfare. Therefore, the very high rating in community collaboration confirms that management is viewed as effective in creating partnerships and external support systems, while also highlighting the need to translate these external gains into fair and inclusive internal benefits.

Table 6: Summary of the Perceived Level of Managerial Competencies

	AWV	SD	Description	Interpretation
A. Leadership Skills	4.49	0.56	Strongly Agree	Very High
B. Resource Management Allocation	4.43	0.66	Strongly Agree	Very High
C. Human Resource Management	4.33	0.75	Strongly Agree	Very High
D. Professional Development Practices	4.38	0.64	Strongly Agree	Very High
E. Community Collaboration	4.47	0.63	Strongly Agree	Very High
Overall	4.42	0.53	Strongly Agree	Very High

AWV=Average Weighted Value, SD=Standard Deviation

Table 6 summarizes the perceived level of managerial competencies. The data show that the respondents perceived the managerial competencies within the college as **very high**, as reflected in the overall mean of 4.42 and standard deviation of 0.53. Among the five domains, leadership skills obtained the highest average weighted value of 4.49, followed by community collaboration with an average weighted value of 4.47. Meanwhile, human resource management obtained the lowest average weighted value of 4.33, although it was still interpreted as very high. This means that the employees generally view their managers as highly competent in leading people, building partnerships, allocating resources, supporting professional development, and managing human resources. The highest rating in leadership skills suggests that employees recognize the ability of management to guide, communicate, make decisions, and influence others toward organizational goals. The very high rating in community collaboration also shows that managers are perceived as capable of establishing linkages and maintaining partnerships that support institutional development. However, the relatively lower rating in human resource management indicates that some areas related to orientation, staff support, performance guidance, and personnel development may still be improved. This suggests that the college has a strong foundation of managerial competence that can contribute to employees' confidence and trust in management. When employees perceive their managers as ethical, capable, participative, and externally engaged, they are more likely to develop positive attitudes toward leadership and institutional goals. Nevertheless, the lower rating in human resource management points to the need for management to give greater attention to internal support systems, especially those related to employee development, fair treatment, performance assistance, and inclusion of both permanent and non-permanent personnel.

The result is supported by Zhu and Zhang (2023), who explained that ethical and competent leadership strengthens employees' confidence because workers tend to trust managers who demonstrate fairness, transparency, and effective decision-making. Their study emphasizes that leadership competence is not limited to administrative ability but also includes relational and ethical behavior that helps develop trust in the workplace. In the same manner, Aboramadan (2022) stressed that human resource management practices are essential in shaping employee trust, particularly in organizations with diverse employment arrangements, because employees are more likely to trust management when they experience support, inclusion, and fairness. Kurtessis et al. (2024) also affirmed that employees' perception of organizational support is strengthened when management provides development opportunities, fair treatment, and consistent assistance. Therefore, the very high rating in managerial competencies confirms that management is generally perceived as capable and effective, while the comparatively lower rating in human resource management indicates the need to further strengthen supportive and equitable personnel practices.

2. What is the respondents' perceived level of trust in management in terms of:

3.1 trust in management competencies;

3.2 trust in management integrity; and

3.3 working relationship?

Table 7: Perceived Level of Trust in Management in Terms of Competencies

A. Trust in Management Competencies	AWV	SD	Description	Interpretation
1. My head of department shows confidence in task performance and administration.	4.60	0.58	Strongly Agree	Very High
2. The ability of my department head is undeniable.	4.64	0.56	Strongly Agree	Very High

3. My department head brings development to the department.	4.71	0.51	Strongly Agree	Very High
4. I have confidence in the ability of my department head.	4.64	0.57	Strongly Agree	Very High
5. My department head is my source of reference.	4.47	0.65	Strongly Agree	Very High
6. My department head can make quick decisions.	4.51	0.69	Strongly Agree	Very High
7. My department head is good at administration.	4.56	0.62	Strongly Agree	Very High
8. My department head has a convincing appearance.	4.63	0.58	Strongly Agree	Very High
9. My department head has great experience in performing his//her tasks.	4.64	0.57	Strongly Agree	Very High
10. My department head is capable of delegating tasks to his//her employees.	4.60	0.61	Strongly Agree	Very High
Overall	4.60	0.52	Strongly Agree	Very High

AWV=Average Weighted Value, SD=Standard Deviation

Table 7 presents the perceived level of trust in management in terms of competencies. The results show that the respondents had a **very high** level of trust in management competencies, as indicated by the overall mean of 4.60 and standard deviation of 0.52. Among the indicators, the highest rating was given to the department head’s role in bringing development to the department, with an average weighted value of 4.71. This was followed by the department head’s undeniable ability, confidence in the ability of the department head, and great experience in performing tasks, each obtaining an average weighted value of 4.64. Meanwhile, the item on the department head being a source of reference obtained the lowest mean of 4.47, although it was still interpreted as very high. This means that employees strongly trust the competence of their department heads. They perceive their leaders as capable, experienced, administratively skilled, and able to make decisions that contribute to departmental development. The very high rating also shows that employees have confidence in the ability of their managers to perform leadership and administrative functions effectively. Although all indicators were rated very high, the slightly lower score on the department head being a source of reference suggests that some employees may still rely on other sources of guidance or may expect more visible mentoring and technical support from management. This implies that managerial competence is an important foundation of employees’ trust in management. When department heads demonstrate capability, confidence, experience, and effective administration, employees are more likely to rely on them and support their decisions. However, management should continue strengthening mentoring, consultation, and knowledge-sharing practices so that department heads are not only viewed as competent administrators but also as accessible sources of professional guidance. Institutionalizing trust-building practices is also necessary so that employees’ trust will not depend solely on individual leaders but will become part of the department’s management culture.

The current finding is supported by Lee and Oh (2023), who emphasized that perceived managerial ability is a major antecedent of trust because employees are more likely to trust leaders who demonstrate competence, sound judgment, and effective administrative performance. Their explanation suggests that trust develops when employees see their leaders as capable of fulfilling responsibilities and making decisions that benefit the organization. Similarly, Gillespie and Dietz (2022) stated that competence-based trust strengthens employee confidence in leadership, especially when managers consistently show reliability, expertise, and effective decision-making. Thus, the very high rating in trust in management competencies confirms that employees perceive their department heads as capable and dependable leaders, thereby supporting the view that managerial competencies serve as a critical foundation of employees’ trust within the college.

Table 8: Perceived Level of Trust in Management in Terms of Management Integrity

B. Management Integrity	AWV	SD	Description	Interpretation
1. My department head is very sincere in performing tasks and in making decisions for the department.	4.74	0.57	Strongly Agree	Very High
2. My department head is a disciplined person in task performance and administration.	4.72	0.55	Strongly Agree	Very High
3. I like the ethical values of my head of department.	4.57	0.69	Strongly Agree	Very High
4. My head of department has high integrity.	4.60	0.64	Strongly Agree	Very High
5. My head of department always shows a good example to his/her employees	4.66	0.60	Strongly Agree	Very High
6. My department head is a person with high principles	4.64	0.60	Strongly Agree	Very High
7. The management of my department head is honest and truthful.	4.66	0.58	Strongly Agree	Very High
8. My department head respects his/her employees.	4.71	0.53	Strongly Agree	Very High
Overall	4.66	0.52	Strongly Agree	Very High

AWV=Average Weighted Value, SD=Standard Deviation

Table 8 presents the perceived level of trust in management in terms of management integrity. The results show that the respondents had a **very high** level of trust in management integrity, as reflected in the overall mean of 4.66 and standard deviation of 0.52. Among the indicators, the highest rating was given to the sincerity of the department head in performing tasks and making decisions for the department, with an average

weighted value of 4.74. This was followed by the department head being disciplined in task performance and administration, with an average weighted value of 4.72, and the department head showing respect for employees, with an average weighted value of 4.71. Meanwhile, the item on liking the ethical values of the department head obtained the lowest mean of 4.57, although it was still interpreted as very high. This means that employees strongly perceive their department heads as sincere, disciplined, respectful, honest, and principled in the performance of their duties. The very high rating indicates that management integrity is one of the strongest foundations of employees' trust in management. Employees appear to believe that their department heads act with fairness, consistency, and moral responsibility, which strengthens their confidence in managerial decisions and leadership actions. This implies that the department heads' integrity plays a vital role in building and sustaining employees' trust. When leaders are perceived as sincere, disciplined, ethical, and respectful, employees are more likely to cooperate, remain committed, and support organizational goals. However, although all indicators were rated very high, the slightly lower rating on ethical values suggests the need for management to continuously demonstrate fairness, transparency, and consistency in decision-making so that employees across different work groups and employment categories will continue to perceive leadership as trustworthy.

The current finding is supported by Li and Li (2023), who emphasized that integrity is a major foundation of trust because employees are more likely to rely on leaders who are perceived as honest, fair, and guided by strong moral principles. In the same manner, Palanski et al. (2021) explained that leader integrity strengthens employee trust because it shows consistency between words, values, and actions. The current finding is also supported by Kim and Beehr (2024), who stated that integrity-based leadership is especially important in diverse organizations because fairness, respect, and ethical conduct help reduce uncertainty among employees, including those in non-permanent or contingent positions. Thus, the very high rating in management integrity confirms that employees view their department heads as ethical and dependable leaders, creating a strong foundation for trust, commitment, and positive workplace relationships.

Table 9: Perceived Level of Trust in Management in Terms of Working Relationship

C. Working Relationship	AWV	SD	Description	Interpretation
1. My department head has good knowledge of my background	4.50	0.62	Strongly Agree	Very High
2. My department head spends time with his/her/her employees	4.54	0.72	Strongly Agree	Very High
3. My department head understands me well	4.46	0.74	Strongly Agree	Very High
4. My department head always discusses work-related issues with his/her employees.	4.53	0.73	Strongly Agree	Very High
Overall	4.51	0.59	Strongly Agree	Very High

AWV=Average Weighted Value, SD=Standard Deviation

Table 9 presents the perceived level of trust in management in terms of working relationships. The results show that the respondents had a **very high** level of trust in management along this dimension, as indicated by the overall mean of 4.51 and standard deviation of 0.59. Among the indicators, the highest rating was given to the department head spending time with employees, with an average weighted value of 4.54, followed by the department head discussing work-related issues with employees, with an average weighted value of 4.53. Meanwhile, the item on the department head understanding employees well obtained the lowest mean of 4.46, although it was still interpreted as very high. This means that employees generally perceive their department heads as approachable, communicative, and willing to engage with them on work-related concerns. The very high rating suggests that management maintains positive working relationships with employees through interaction, consultation, and open discussion. However, the slightly lower rating on being well understood indicates that some employees may still feel that management needs to deepen its awareness of their individual circumstances, needs, and workplace experiences.

This implies that while trust in working relationships is already strong, there is still room for management to further strengthen personalized and inclusive engagement with employees. Department heads may improve this dimension by regularly checking on employees' concerns, maintaining open communication, recognizing the different needs of permanent and non-permanent personnel, and creating opportunities for meaningful dialogue. Since working relationship obtained a slightly lower rating compared with management integrity and trust in competencies, relational leadership may be considered an important area for sustaining and deepening employees' trust in management.

The current finding is supported by Zhang and Chen (2023), who emphasized that relational trust is built through consistent communication, personal interaction, and affective bonds between leaders and employees. Their study explains that while employees may easily recognize competence and integrity, the development of deeper working relationships requires continuous interpersonal engagement and understanding. Similarly, Lee and Wang (2024) stated that leaders who maintain open communication and spend time with employees are more likely to promote psychological safety, engagement, and trust. Hence, the current finding confirms that the department heads are perceived as accessible and communicative, but it also suggests that greater attention should be given to developing deeper personalized understanding across diverse groups of employees.

Table 10: Summary of the Perceived Level of Trust in Management

	AWV	SD	Description	Interpretation
A. Trust in Management Competencies	4.60	0.52	Strongly Agree	Very high
B. Management Integrity	4.66	0.52	Strongly Agree	Very high
C. Working Relationship	4.51	0.59	Strongly Agree	Very high
Overall	4.59	0.60	Strongly Agree	Very high

AWV=Average Weighted Value, SD=Standard Deviation

Table 10 summarizes the perceived level of trust in management. The data reveal that the respondents had a very high level of trust in management, as shown by the overall mean of 4.59 with a standard deviation of 0.60. Among the three indicators, management integrity obtained the highest rating with an average weighted value of 4.66, followed by trust in management competencies with an average weighted value of 4.60. Meanwhile, **working relationship** obtained the lowest rating with an average weighted value of 4.51, although it was still interpreted as very high. This means that employees strongly trust their managers, especially in terms of honesty, sincerity, ethical conduct, and consistency in decision-making. The highest rating for management integrity suggests that employees view their department heads as principled, fair, and trustworthy. The very high rating for trust in management competencies also indicates that employees believe their managers are capable of performing administrative and leadership responsibilities effectively. However, the slightly lower rating for working relationship means that although employees generally have positive relationships with management, interpersonal closeness, mutual understanding, and regular work-related interaction may still vary among respondents. This implies that trust in management within the college is strongly anchored on the perceived integrity and competence of department heads. Employees are more likely to cooperate, support institutional goals, and maintain positive work behavior when they perceive their managers as ethical, capable, and reliable. Nevertheless, management may further strengthen trust by improving relational leadership practices, such as spending more time with employees, understanding their needs, maintaining open communication, and promoting inclusive interactions across employment groups. Since working relationship obtained the lowest mean among the indicators, this area may be considered a priority for sustaining and deepening employees' trust.

The current finding is supported by Mayer and Schoorman (2021), who emphasized that trust in management is shaped by employees' perceptions of a leader's ability, integrity, and benevolence. Their explanation suggests that employees are more willing to rely on managers when they believe that these leaders are competent, honest, and guided by sound moral principles. Similarly, Dawes et al. (2024) stated that integrity remains a central foundation of organizational trust because employees tend to place greater confidence in leaders who demonstrate fairness, transparency, and consistency in their actions. The current finding is also supported by Zhang and Li (2023), who noted that strong working relationships between leaders and employees help sustain trust, but relational trust may differ across groups depending on communication patterns, employment status, and daily workplace interaction. Thus, the very high trust rating in this study confirms that employees generally perceive management as ethical and competent, while the relatively lower rating in working relationship suggests the need to further strengthen interpersonal engagement within the organization.

3. Is there a significant relationship between the perceived level of managerial competencies and the perceived level of trust in management?

Table 11: Test of Relationship between the Levels of Management Competencies and Trust in Management

Variables Correlated	rho-value	p-value	Interpretation
Management Competencies and Trust in Management	0.37	< 0.01	Medium/Moderate Positive Correlation Significant

Table 11 presents the test of relationship between the perceived level of managerial competencies and the perceived level of trust in management. Using the Spearman Rank-Order Correlation Coefficient, the result revealed a rho value of 0.37 with a p-value of less than 0.01. This indicates a statistically significant moderate positive relationship between managerial competencies and employees' trust in management. Since the p-value is lower than the 0.05 level of significance, the null hypothesis stating that there is no significant relationship between managerial competencies and trust in management is rejected. This means that as employees perceive managerial competencies to be higher, their trust in management also tends to increase. The moderate positive correlation suggests that competent management practices, such as effective leadership, fair resource allocation, sound human resource management, support for professional development, and community collaboration, contribute to the development of employees' confidence in management. However, the moderate strength of the relationship also shows that managerial competencies are not the only factors that influence trust. Other factors, such as integrity, fairness, communication practices, employment security, campus climate, and personal working relationships, may also affect how employees develop trust in their managers. This implies that strengthening managerial competencies remains an important strategy in improving employees' trust in management. Managers who demonstrate clear communication, ethical decision-making, fairness, and professional capability are more likely to gain the confidence of employees. Nevertheless, management should not focus only on technical and administrative competence. It should also give attention to relational and ethical aspects of leadership, including sincerity, transparency, respect, and consistency, since these qualities further strengthen trust-based working relationships within the organization.

The present finding is supported by Mayer et al. (1995), who explained that ability or competence is one of the major foundations of organizational trust, together with benevolence and integrity. Their trust model suggests that employees are more likely to trust leaders whom they perceive as capable, reliable, and effective in performing their responsibilities. Similarly, Khan et al. (2023) affirmed that managerial competence significantly contributes to employees' trust because competent leaders are viewed as dependable and capable of making decisions that support organizational goals. Furthermore, Zhu and Zhang (2023) emphasized that trust in leadership is strengthened not only by competence but also by ethical behavior, transparent communication, and relational fairness. Therefore, the present finding confirms that managerial competencies positively influence employees' trust in management, while also suggesting that trust is shaped by broader ethical, relational, and contextual factors.

DISCUSSION

The findings reveal that both managerial competencies and trust in management within the College of Business Administration were perceived at a very high level, indicating that employees generally view their department heads as ethical, capable, communicative, supportive, and

development-oriented leaders. Leadership skills and community collaboration emerged as the strongest areas of managerial competence, while human resource management, although still very high, appeared as the area needing further strengthening, particularly in staff orientation, performance guidance, coaching, and equitable support for permanent and non-permanent employees. In terms of trust, management integrity obtained the highest rating, showing that employees strongly perceive their leaders as sincere, disciplined, respectful, honest, and principled, while working relationship obtained the lowest rating among the trust indicators, suggesting the need to deepen interpersonal communication and personalized engagement. The results that that trust in management differed by campus, indicating that campus-specific leadership experiences and organizational climate may influence trust. Finally, the significant moderate positive relationship between managerial competencies and trust in management confirms that competent leadership contributes to employee trust, although trust is also shaped by other factors such as fairness, integrity, communication, job security, and working relationships.

CONCLUSION

Based on the findings, the study concludes that the managerial competencies of the College of Business Administration management were perceived to be very high, particularly in leadership skills and community collaboration, while human resource management, though still very high, appeared to need further strengthening. Employees also demonstrated a very high level of trust in management, especially in terms of management integrity, showing that department heads were viewed as sincere, ethical, disciplined, respectful, and dependable. Furthermore, the significant moderate positive relationship between managerial competencies and trust in management led to the rejection of the null hypothesis, which means that higher perceived managerial competence is associated with higher employees' trust. Overall, the findings indicate that competent, ethical, participative, and development-oriented management helps build and sustain employees' trust, although other factors such as fairness, communication, employment security, institutional climate, and working relationships may also influence trust.

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